

A tracer study of Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology students from Batch 2018 to 2021

Eurich Roi C. Araneta*

Radiologic Technology Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author: eurichroi_araneta@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Radiological technology is an allied healthcare profession that deals with producing internal and external images of the human body that are needed for prognosis and diagnosis. Also, they use certain modalities that can have a therapeutic effect on the patient. Being given such responsibilities, they are called the “eye of the medicine,” which clearly shows how important their role in medicine is. With that, the demand for radiologic technologists is increasing. The tracer study that covered BSRT alumni members from batch 2018 to 2021 applied a non-experimental descriptive study for its research design. There were 40 total respondents, which represented the total population of this study. The researcher used a survey questionnaire via Google Forms to gather data. The questionnaire comprises four (4) parts: the respondent’s classification, licensure examination, post-graduate studies, and employment status. The study found out that our graduates, particularly under the BS Radiologic Technology program of St. Dominic College of Asia, have the desired attributes and competencies that are very much important in their chosen working area. This also shows that most of the respondents have landed a job several months after their graduation and after they have passed their licensure examination for radiologic technology. With that, it can be considered that the employment rate of our graduates is employable. It is recommended that the BSRT department should come up with an activity such as a seminar or webinar that will focus on the importance and the advantages of pursuing post-graduate studies.

Keywords: Tracer study; Radiologic technology; St. Dominic College of Asia; Job hiring.

To cite this article:

Araneta, E. R. C. (2021). A tracer study of Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology students from Batch 2018 to 2021. *SDCA Journal of Radiologic Technology*, 2, 1-4.

Introduction

Radiological technology is an allied healthcare profession that deals with producing internal and external images of the human body that are needed for the prognosis and diagnosis (Khong et al., 2013; Rogers et al., 2020; Rystedt et al., 2011). Also, they use certain modalities that can have a therapeutic effect on the patient. Being given such responsibilities, they are called the “eye of the medicine,” which clearly shows how important their role in medicine is. With that, the demand for radiologic technologists is increasing. According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, there is an increase in demand for radiologic and MRI technologists from 9% in the year 2020 to 2030, with roughly 20,800 openings for radiologic and MRI technologists each year (Cleveland University-Kansas City, n.d.).

Several tracer studies related to Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology (BSRT) were conducted by different authors, particularly from schools and universities in the Philippines. Daquis et al. (2016) found that the reasons why radiologic technology graduates from Lyceum of the Philippines University in Batangas City accept and remain on the job are the career challenge and the connection between the course work and the job assignment, which contribute much to their employment. Pambid and Agawin (2020) discovered that the Radiologic Technology program is an effective course for students at the Lyceum of the Philippines University-Laguna Campus, where graduates can find work quickly, while most respondents were able to secure their first employment within three months, most especially at St. Frances Cabrini Medical Center, and some of them were able to do so even prior to graduating. Talaroc et al. (2021) conducted a study on licensure examination among radiologic technology graduates from Iligan Medical Center College, Iligan City, Lanao del Norte, wherein student internship grade (SIG), college admission test (CAT), and terminal competency assessment (TCA) scores contribute to the licensure examination performance, while those with low scores resulted in low performance in the licensure examinations.

With those articles, the vision and mission of the BSRT department in this institution, which is producing competitive graduates locally and globally, it is a must that the department should strictly evaluate and design the curriculum to facilitate more effective learning among their students (Gutierrez, 2020; Prier & Ayars, 2021; Wilson et al., 2018). This tracer study primarily determined the status of BSRT graduates from batch 2018 to 2021. Specifically, it also aims to determine the status of their graduates, be it in their performance for the licensure examination of Radiologic Technology, their post-graduate studies, or their employment status.

Methodology

The tracer study that covered BSRT alumni from batch 2018 to 2021 applied a non-experimental descriptive study for its research design. There were 40 total respondents from batch 2018 until batch 2021, which represented the total population of this study. The researcher used a survey questionnaire via Google Forms to gather data. The questionnaire comprises four (4) parts: the respondent's classification (from what batch), licensure examination, post-graduate studies, and employment status. Other respondents' information, such as names, addresses, and cellular numbers, were not asked for anymore. The information gathered was tallied and coded in preparation for the analysis. Frequencies and percentages were used to determine the status of alumni members for BSRT.

The image shows a Google Form titled "TRACER STUDIES AY 2018 - 2021". The form is designed with a light purple border and contains several sections. At the top, it displays the title and the user's email address, "eurichroi_araneta@sdca.edu.ph", with a "Switch account" link. Below this, there is a note: "Your email will be recorded when you submit this form" and a red asterisk indicating a required field. The first question is "From which batch were you graduated? *", with radio button options for 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021. The second question is "Did you passed your licensure examination? *", with radio button options for "yes" and "no". The third question is "Did you take the licensure examination for Radiologic Technology? *", also with radio button options for "yes" and "no". The fourth question is "Did you pursue a post-graduate studies such as medicine proper, master/doctoral, and the likes... *", with radio button options for "yes" and "no". A fifth question is partially visible: "Are you currently employed related to Radiologic Technology? *". At the bottom of the form, there is a purple "Submit" button and a "Clear form" link.

Figure 1. Sample questionnaire

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Summary of the Gathered Data from the Respondents (n = 40)

Batch	1. Distributions of respondents per Batch		2. Number of respondents who took the licensure exam		3. Number of respondents who passed their licensure exam		4. Number of respondents who pursue post-graduate studies		5. Number of respondents who are currently employed as RT		6. Number of respondents who are currently employed unrelated to RT	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
2018	11	27.5%	10	90.9%	8	80%	0	0%	8	72.3%	3	27.3%
2019	6	15%	6	100%	4	66.7%	0	0%	3	50%	3	50%
2020	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
2021	23	57.5%	14	60.9%	8	57.1%	1	0.04%	4	17.4%	12	52.2%

Legend: f – frequency, % – percentage

The data presented above revealed that there are 40 total respondents, and the majority of those came from batch 2021, comprising 57.5% of the total population. This is then followed by batch 2018 with 27.5%, then from batch 2019 with 15%. Lastly, it was observed that there were no representatives from batch 2020. This is because those graduating students from batch 2020 failed to finish their thesis writing. As for the number of respondents who took the licensure exam, it was clear that only from batch 2019 did the graduated students all take their licensure exam. While only 90.9% and 60.9% took their licensure examination from batch 2018 and 2021, respectively. On the brighter side, most of the licensure examination takers passed it, with an 80% passing rate from batch 2018, a 66.7% passing rate from RT batch 2019, and a 57.1% passing rate from batch 2021.

As for the number of respondents who pursue post-graduate studies, be it in medicine proper, law proper, a master's and/or doctoral degree, and the like, only one (1) student from batch 2021 did it. The last category is about employment status; most graduates from batch 2018, or 72.3%, are currently employed and connected to their chosen profession. In the batch of 2019, there is an even distribution of those graduate students who are working as radiographers or working that is not related to radiography. Moreover, from batch 2021, most of the respondents, which equals 52.2%, were working in jobs not related to radiologic technology. Maybe this is because they are quite afraid of exposing themselves to COVID-19.

An article from You Unlimited (2020) entitled “*10 Tips for Improving Your Employability*” tells the 10 simplest ways on how an individual can improve his/her chances of being employed: sharpening the C-skills, which include communication, creativity, curiosity, collaboration, cooperation, and caring in the work; shining up the curriculum vitae; seeking trusted career advice from family, friends, and colleagues; directing your own learning; spotlighting your experiences; building your social media profile; being a better storyteller; being always prepared in any type of interview; growing your professional network; and developing a growth mindset.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study found out that the graduates, particularly under BS Radiologic Technology of St. Dominic College of Asia, have the desired attributes and competencies that are very much important in their chosen working area. This also shows that most of the respondents have landed a job several months after their graduation and after they have passed their licensure examination for radiologic technology. With that, it can be considered that the employment rate of our graduates is employable.

Based on the findings, it is quite saddening that only one student pursues post-graduate studies. Therefore, it is recommended that the BSRT department should come up with an activity such as a seminar

or webinar that will focus on the importance and the advantages of pursuing post-graduate studies. Also, although the figures show a good employability rate of the graduates, the BSRT department should go beyond the miles in helping their graduates in securing a job by introducing them to other colleagues working in the hospital and different Facebook groups specifically for RT job hiring or a possibility in absorbing their deserving graduate to be part of this institution. Lastly, to ensure that all the graduates of this institution will possess the desired attributes and competencies that most companies were looking for, it is a must that the students should be trained in their leadership and team member skills by giving them a lot of training and simulations of what the world is like in professional life.

References

- Cleveland University-Kansas City. (n.d.). *A radiologic technology degree expands your options*.
<https://www.cleveland.edu/a-radiologic-technology-degree-expands-your-options-2/>
- Daquis, M. A., Caparas, A. M., Zerrudo, J. I., & Mercado, L. M. (2016). Employability of BS Radiologic Technology graduates from 2013 to 2015 as input to student development program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences*, 3(4), 91-99.
https://www.academia.edu/32972468/Employability_of_BS_Radiologic_Technology_Graduates_from_2013_to_2015_as_Input_to_Student_Development_Program
- Gutierrez, M. J. P. (2020). A tracer study of BSRT students from Batch 2015 to 2017. *SDCA Journal of Radiologic Technology*, 1, 16-22.
- Khong, P. L., Ringertz, H., Donoghue, V., Frush, D., Rehani, M., Appelgate, K., & Sanchez, R. (2013). ICRP publication 121: radiological protection in paediatric diagnostic and interventional radiology. *Annals of the ICRP*, 42(2), 1-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icrp.2012.10.001>
- Pambid, D., & Agawin, M. (2020). A tracer study of radiologic technology graduates of LPU-ST. Cabrini College of Allied Medicine from 2016-2018. *LPU-Laguna Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(1), 78-84. https://lpulaguna.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/7.-Pambid-Agawin_GTS-Radtech.pdf
- Prier, J., & Ayars, C. (2021). Evaluation of ethics curricula and faculty in accredited undergraduate radiologic technology programs. *Radiologic Technology*, 92(4), 331-344.
<http://www.radiologictechnology.org/content/92/4/331.short>
- Rogers, W., Thulasi Seetha, S., Refaee, T. A., Lieverse, R. I., Granzier, R. W., Ibrahim, A., Keek, S. A., Sanduleanu, S., Primakov, S. P., Beuque, M. P. L., Marcus, D., van der Wiel, A. M. A., Zerka, F., Oberije, C. J. G., van Timmeren, J. E., Woodruff, H. C., & Lambin, P. (2020). Radiomics: from qualitative to quantitative imaging. *The British Journal of Radiology*, 93(1108), 20190948.
<https://doi.org/10.1259/bjr.20190948>
- Rystedt, H., Ivarsson, J., Asplund, S., Johnsson, Å. A., & Båth, M. (2011). Rediscovering radiology: New technologies and remedial action at the worksite. *Social Studies of Science*, 41(6), 867-891.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312711423433>
- Talaroc, F. R., Ali, A., & Alipio, M. (2021). Factors associated with licensure examination performance of radiologic technology graduates. *IMCC Journal of Science*, 1(1), 46-55.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED618547.pdf>
- Wilson, J. S., Alvarez, J., Davis, B. C., & Duerinckx, A. J. (2018). Cost-effective teaching of radiology with preclinical anatomy. *Anatomical Sciences Education*, 11(2), 196-206.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ase.1710>
- You Unlimited. (2020, July 7). *10 tips for improving your employability*.
<https://www.younlimitedanz.com/be-inspired/articles/10-tips-for-improving-your-employability>